

Kinetics of Ring Opening of Epoxides

B. K. Chanda, J. N. Kar, G. B. Behera and M. K. Rout*

A few appropriately substituted epoxides have been prepared and their kinetics of ring opening with thiosulphate ion have been studied. The reaction has been found to be of second order. Increase in ionic strength decreases the rate of reaction in accordance with Amis-Jaffe equation¹ except at higher ionic strength value. From the slope of the straight line plots of $\log k$ and $1/D$ at various temperatures the dipole moment values of epoxides at 40°, 45° and 50° have been evaluated to be 1.2D, 1.4D and 2.0D respectively. With substituted epoxides electron withdrawing groups increase the rate of reaction. The compensation law² is found to be obeyed. The rate constants of different substituted epoxides have been correlated with σ^+ values. The value of σ^+ is +0.714 indicating a bimolecular reaction. The decrease in the rate of reaction due to ortho-substituents has been explained on the basis of a probable transition state proposed.

Epoxides are known to act as electrophilic reagents and it has been demonstrated that they react readily with proteins at physiological pH^3 . This led to the testing of various diepoxides and the establishment of their radiomimetic properties⁴. The efficiency of a compound as a tumour growth inhibitor runs parallel with its relative reactivity towards nucleophilic centre, a property conveniently assessed by measuring the rate of reaction of epoxides. Much work has not been done on the influence of substituents on kinetics in the reactions of epoxides. In view of this, the kinetics of ring opening of the oxide ring have been undertaken in the present investigation to assess the electrophilic ability of differently substituted epoxides.

EXPERIMENTAL

The epoxides (except 2/- and 3/-nitro) were prepared by epoxidation of appropriately substituted chalcones with alkaline hydrogen peroxide. 2/- and 3/-Nitro chalcone epoxides were prepared from phenacyl bromide and *o*-nitro or *m*-nitro benzaldehyde by the method of Ballester and Bartlett⁵. The epoxides were purified by crystallising from alcohol.

Kinetic measurement : 25 ml of epoxide (0.02 *M*) in absolute ethanol and 25 ml of sodium thiosulphate (0.125 *M*) in water were preheated to the required temperature in a thermostat ($\pm 0.01^\circ$) and then mixed together. A stop watch was started concurrently. The alkalinity developed was titrated at different time intervals against acetic acid using phenolphthalein as indicator.

Present address : Principal, Ravenshaw College, Cuttack.

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The first order rate constants were calculated by employing the equation.

$$k = \frac{2.303}{t} \log \frac{100}{(100 - \% \text{ Ester})}$$

The reaction has been studied to an extent of 33% to avoid any complication due to back reaction. Values for the energy of activation have been evaluated from the slopes of the straight line plots of $\log k$ vs. $1/T$. The reaction has also been studied at different concentrations of salt.

RESULTS

TABLE I

Rate data at different thiosulphate concentrations.

[Epoxide] = 0.0125 (M); Temp. = 40°					
[S ₂ O ₃ ²⁻]	0.1	0.08	0.06	0.04	0.02
k × 10 ⁵ in sec. ⁻¹	2.772	2.559	2.111	1.244	0.7381
$\frac{k \times 10^5}{[S_2O_3^{2-}]}$	27.72	31.98	35.20	33.60	36.40

TABLE II

Rate data at various epoxide concentrations.

[S ₂ O ₃ ²⁻] = 0.02(M); Temp. = 40°				
Epoxide		0.015	0.01	0.008
k × 10 ⁵ in sec. ⁻¹		1.185	0.738	0.7078
$\frac{k \times 10^5}{[\text{Epoxide}]}$	in litre mole ⁻¹ sec. ⁻¹	7.9	7.38	8.847

TABLE III

Values for rate constants, frequency factor, energy, entropy and free energy of activation values.

Name of the substituents	35°	10 ⁵ × k in sec. ⁻¹		50°	E in k cal/mole	log PZ	-ΔS‡ in e.u.	ΔF‡ in k cal
		40°	45°					
3'-Nitro-		6.226	9.404	13.51	15.50	6.54	28.89	24.54
4'-Chloro-		3.71	4.912	7.676	14.54	5.66	32.97	24.86
4'-Methoxy-	1.213	2.302	2.81	3.096	11.52	3.35	43.61	25.17
Hydrogen-		2.091	2.584	3.870	12.32	3.86	41.23	25.22
4'-Methyl-		1.204	1.873	2.373	13.57	4.49	38.34	25.57
2'-Nitro-		2.974	1.909	2.617	19.77	8.71	18.92	25.69
2'-Chloro-		0.92	1.132	1.466	11.24	2.76	46.34	25.74
2'-Methoxy-		0.613	0.87	1.251	14.01	4.50	38.31	26.00

TABLE IV

Rate data at different ethanol-water mixtures.

% of Water	$k \times 10^5$ in sec. ⁻¹		
	40°	45°	50°
40	1.344	1.54	2.59
45	1.439	1.957	3.262
50	2.091	2.584	3.87
52.5	2.417	3.24	5.174

TABLE V

Effect of salt.

Conc. of NaCl in (M)	40°	$k \times 10^5$ in sec. ⁻¹ 45°	50°	E in k cal/mole	log PZ	$-\Delta S \neq$ e.u.	$\Delta F \neq$ k cal/mole
0.05	1.775	2.302	3.531	13.83	4.83	36.76	25.32
0.10	1.492	2.072	3.166	15.36	5.82	32.21	25.44
0.15	1.279	2.111	2.974	17.28	7.09	26.35	25.53
0.20	1.295	2.175	3.206	15.36	5.76	32.48	25.52

DISCUSSION

The epoxide ring is opened by an anion in the following manner :

So the rate of the reaction has been followed by measuring the rate of increase in alkalinity in the reaction mixture.

Order of reaction : Ring opening of epoxides has been studied at various concentrations of thiosulphate and epoxide (Table I and II). The reaction is found to be a second order process. By using large excess of thiosulphate the reaction has been made to obey first order rate law.

Effect of salt : The effects of the ionic strength on the epoxide ring opening by the thiosulphate has been studied at various temperatures (Table V). It can be observed from the table that as the ionic strength increases the velocity constant decreases. The trend of this variation is, however, reversed at higher ionic strength. This effect of ionic strength is in agreement with Amis-Jaffe equation¹,

$$\ln k' = \ln k_{D=\infty} + \frac{Ze\mu_0}{DkTr_0^2} + \frac{Ze\cos\theta}{DkTr_0^2} \left[\mu_0^* - \frac{\mu^*(1+xr_0)}{e^{\alpha r_0}} \right]$$

The values for the energy of activation (Table V) increase with increasing concentration of the salt but at higher concentration, it decreases. This might be due to the polarisation which the cation exerts on the electron of the anion when an ion pair is formed or when the cation is near enough to the activated complex.

Effect of dielectric constant: The rate data for the unsubstituted epoxide at various temperatures at different ethanol-water mixtures are given in Table IV. These data are fitted to the equation,

$$\ln k'_{D=D} = \ln k'_{D=\infty} + \frac{Ze\mu_0}{DkT\tau^2}$$

and a straight line plot is obtained between $\ln k'_{D=D}$ and $1/D$. Assuming the value of $r(=1.5\text{\AA})$, the dipole moment of the epoxide has been calculated to be $1.2D$, $1.4D$ and $2.0D$ at 40° , 45° and 50° respectively.

Substituent effect: Order of reactivity: It is observed from the rate data given in Table III that the reactivity of different substituents conform to the order:

Entropy-Energy relationship: The values for the entropies of activation for the reaction under study are negative. This may be explained by the greater compactness of the transition state as compared to the ground state causing a restriction in the number of configurations which the atoms involved may assume; thus the entropy of the system is decreased. The highly negative values for the entropy of activation also suggest (i) the bimolecular nature of the reaction and (ii) that the ring is not broken in the transition state since the transformation from a vibrational to a rotational degree of freedom should result in a positive contribution to ΔS^\ddagger , the magnitude of which could be as high as 7.5 e.u. ΔS^\ddagger values systematically change with ΔH^\ddagger values and are related by an equation:

$$\Delta H^\ddagger/E = \Delta H_0^\ddagger(E_0) + \beta\Delta S^\ddagger.$$

The values of E_0 and β have been found to be $2600 k$ cal/mole and 330°K respectively. A linear energy-entropy relationship suggests a compensation of the activation parameters and hence operation of the same mechanism in its main details.

Applicability of Hammett equation: Since it was observed that $\log k$ values did not correlate well with Hammett sigma values, the values of rate constants were fitted to the equation $\log k/k_0 = \rho^+\sigma^+$. The points for methoxy and chloro did not lie on the line indicating resonance contribution due to these substituents. The value of ρ^+ has been calculated to be $+0.714$ which is expected of a typical SN_2 reaction.

The increased rate of reaction due to electron withdrawing groups and the entropy considerations discussed above suggest the transition state to be a negatively charged one. Since the epoxide can be stereochemically represented as

the probable transition state for the reaction may be formulated as

With the transition state proposed, the effect of orthosubstituents can be explained. The order of reactivity of the ortho-substituents is $-\text{NO}_2 > \text{Cl} > -\text{OCH}_3$ which is consistent with the nature of the reaction. There is a possibility of hydrogen bond formation with the ortho-methoxy and ortho-methyl groups thereby stabilising the transition state. But the rate is decreased because of electronic effects.

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Department of Chemistry,
Ravenshaw College,
Cuttack-3.

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